

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AFSINA bearing USN 6SU20CP801 has completed his/her internship at The Saffaron foundation Mangalore in the first Semester of the MSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms FASMIN YOUSUF bearing USN 6SU20CP802 has completed his/her internship at The Saffaron foundation Mangalore in the first Semester of the MSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms JOYCE ANJANA RODRIGUES bearing USN 6SU20CP803 has completed his/her internship at The Saffaron foundation Mangalore in the first Semester of the MSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms KEERTHANA SATHYAN bearing USN 6SU20CP804 has completed his/her internship at The Saffaron foundation Mangalore in the first Semester of the MSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MARY DEVASIA C bearing USN 6SU20CP805 has completed his/her internship at The Saffaron foundation Mangalore in the first Semester of the MSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms RAKSHITHA bearing USN 6SU20CP806 has completed his/her internship at The Saffaron foundation Mangalore in the first Semester of the MSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms RESHMA BASHEER MOOCHIKKAL bearing USN 6SU20CP807 has completed his/her internship at The Saffaron foundation Mangalore in the first Semester of the MSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SAHANA D bearing USN 6SU20CP808 has completed his/her internship at The Saffaron foundation Mangalore in the first Semester of the MSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHANY CHERIYAN bearing USN 6SU20CP809 has completed his/her internship at The Saffaron foundation Mangalore in the first Semester of the MSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SUNBULA T bearing USN 6SU20CP810 has completed his/her internship at The Saffaron foundation Mangalore in the first Semester of the MSc. Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146